

Mindfulness, Quantum Physics and “well-being is a two-way street”.
Olga Nickole Kuyan

Abstract

The Law Gazette article “Well-being is a two-way street, judge tells ‘wildly optimistic’” touches, *inter alia*, two important issues: well-being and golden rule. While *quasi* all people have heard about the well-being and the golden rule, only some people have met it in their lives. The well-being and the golden rule are the desirable things for lawyers/judges, for everybody. But do you often see case parties or clients who take care of judge/lawyer’s well-being? It’s another side of the golden rule. *Et sic*, judges/lawyers have to take care of their well-being. And how to remain thankful, polite and kind judge/lawyer? Lawyers operate and work within the context of complex human situations – predominantly situations of conflict and stress – and attempt to apply a body of external laws, rules and practices to resolve those situations and conflicts. This is within a framework of time, financial, epidemic and other external pressures. What could we advise to judges/lawyers? How could we apply the golden rule here? We put forward the idea on the evolution towards Judges/Lawyers Wellbeing and Justice through Mindfulness.

Keywords: well-being, golden rule, judge, lawyer, the mind–body problem, spirituality, evolution, mindfulness-based interventions, attention, intention, non judgmental way, Mediterranean lifestyle, quantum physics

The Law Gazette article “Well-being is a two-way street, judge tells ‘wildly optimistic’”¹ touches, *inter alia*, two important issues: well-being and golden rule. “Chandler said: ‘Just as practitioners should not receive unreasonable demands from the judiciary, so judges should not be put in the sort of position this court faced in the present case: wellbeing is a two-way street. Realistic time estimates must be given’.”²

While *quasi* all people have heard about the well-being and the golden rule, only some people have met it in their lives. Well-being and the golden rule are the desirable things for lawyers/judges, for everybody. But do you often see case parties or clients who take care of judge/lawyer’s well-being? It’s another side of the golden rule. *Et sic*, judges/lawyers have to take care of themselves. And how to remain thankful, polite and kind judge/lawyer?

Lawyers/judges operate and work within the context of complex human situations – predominantly situations of conflict and stress – and attempt to apply a body of external laws, rules and practices to resolve those situations and conflicts. This is within a framework of time, financial, epidemic and other external pressures.

What could we advice to judges/lawyers? How could we apply the golden rule here?

It’s a matter of the rule of law, to fulfill our role of stewardship by insulating justice/good lawyering against the challenges of the future.

We introduce a well-being form of the modified Mediterranean Style of Life that resolves a broad spectrum of crisis and stress problems.

We confirm that a traditional Mediterranean lifestyle engages regularly in mindfulness. It is a mindfulness-based stress reduction and usual care during working day for reducing stress and adverse it outcomes. The researchers found that a high adherence to a Mediterranean lifestyle means a lower likelihood of developing depression, stress or its symptoms.³

We put forward the idea on ***the Evolution*** towards ***Judges/Lawyers Wellbeing*** and ***Justice, Good Lawyering*** through ***Mindfulness***.

1 <https://www.lawgazette.co.uk/news/wellbeing-is-a-two-way-street-judge-tells-wildly-optimistic-lawyers/5110435.article>

2 Ibid.

3 <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/325240#A-link-that-warrants-further-study>

We don't use the term *Evolution* in its Darwinian-Lamarckian sense. We use it in J.J. Hurtak's⁴ sense: *true evolution is spiritual/mindfulness (consciousness) evolution*.

While many empirical studies have confirmed that regular mindfulness meditation can have beneficial effects on people's well-being, so far very little is known about the contribution of mindfulness to lawyering, judiciary and justice.

By the definite science of meditation known for millenniums to the yogis and sages of India, and to Jesus, any lawyer, any judge, any professional, anybody and everybody, "can enlarge the caliber of his consciousness to omniscience to receive within himself the Universal Intelligence of God."⁵

Over the past few decades, mindfulness meditation has become increasingly popular. A woolly concept for many, mindfulness has been described as being "not about feeling better, it is about being better at feeling". The Oxford on-line dictionary describes mindfulness as, "A mental state achieved by focusing one's awareness on the present moment, while calmly acknowledging and accepting one's feelings, thoughts, and bodily sensations, used as a therapeutic technique".⁶

Judge/lawyer uses discretion/creativity, interprets legal norms, applies them to the circumstances. He/she is a thinker, a decision-maker. Mindful thinking is the ability to be aware and conscious of your thoughts. Mindful judicial discretion/legal creativity is to be aware and conscious of your thoughts regarding application and interpretation of legal norms in a just way. To ground yourself in the present case/legal issue, acknowledging what you are thinking and feeling – but without being reactive to it. Being mindful judge/lawyer means being aware of your thoughts, emotions, and how you're feeling both physically and mentally.

The impact of mindfulness is already widely recognised and appreciated in the fields of medicine, psychology, education and business but the legal profession has been slower to accept and integrate its transformative effects. Meditation retreats for lawyers are still relatively rare on this side of the world however in the US they are more common. The fact that lawyers are more sceptical than most, is perhaps the key reason why mindfulness has been slower to take off in the legal profession. The reported benefits of mindfulness meditation practice are numerous and varied. These include reduced stress, improved well-being, increased immune functioning, boost to memory and focus, increased relationship satisfaction enhanced self-insight, morality and intuition. Some benefits of mindfulness are obvious but others, no less important, are less so because they are more subtle. Legal academics cite these additional potential benefits, as follows:

1. Increasing the ability to transcend the dominating influence of the traditional adversarial mind-set to allow awareness of other perspectives;
2. Developing the skill of deep and open listening;
3. Developing negotiation skills by training in the maintenance of a delicate balance (in understanding, emotion and behaviour) necessary for making wise decisions;
4. Fostering the ability for calm deliberation, which promotes better decision-making in difficult situations;
5. Cultivating trial advocacy skills by developing internal abilities to, for example, remain centred in challenging moments in court and retain authenticity;
6. Enhancing the performance of traditional legal tasks, such as learning, understanding and manipulating rules of law, drafting documents and litigating cases;
7. Enhancing ethical practice through, for example, developing the self-reflection skills important to judgment and also because mindfulness makes it more likely that one will adopt universal norms such as honesty and fairness;
8. Making the practice of law more meaningful and satisfying generally;

4 J.J. Hurtak (born 1940, sometimes referred to as James Jacob) is an American social scientist, linguist, futurist, and author. Hurtak's work encompasses a diverse array of disciplines, including religion and philosophy, space law, environmental sciences, remote sensing, and unconventional theories in the fields of planetary sciences and archaeology. Through the "Academy for Future Science," Hurtak works internationally to encourage people to embrace new and emerging technologies.

5 Paramahansa Yogananda, <https://yogananda.org/kriya-yoga-path-of-meditation-history>

6 <https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/mindfulness>

9. Expanding focus to include broader orientations towards lawyering (for example, restorative justice, therapeutic jurisprudence, collaborative law and other healing, peace-making perspectives).⁷ We hypothesize that:

- good lawyering/justice depend upon the judicial discretion/legal creativity,
- the creativity/discretion is based on the mindfulness (consciousness),
- the legal consciousness makes the part of awareness and mindfulness;
- the mindfulness is the road to justice/good lawyering and well-being.

The mindfulness means awareness (consciousness) but in a particular sense. It refers first of all to direct experience. The experience deals with attention. Among the possible descriptions, that of Jon Kabat-Zinn, has become “classic”: “Mindfulness means paying attention, but in a particular way: a) with intention, b) in the present moment, c) in a non-judgmental way”.⁸ It can also be described as a way to cultivate a fuller presence in the experience of the moment, in the here and now.

It sic, regarding just legal services/justice the mindfulness means attention with intention in a present trial/case/legal issue in a non judgmental way.

Attention. In the field of justice/just legal services, attention (experienced-based practice) is essential in validating the discretion/creativity within the judiciary/legal community. *Discretio est discernere per legem quid sit justum.*⁹

Mindfulness is a general term for using the “present moment as the core indicator of the appropriateness of particular choices”¹⁰ (Kabat-Zinn).

Intention. At its base, mindfulness is a natural human state in which an individual experiences and attends to the present moment. Recently an intervention based on the Buddhist principles of awareness, called mindfulness, has become increasingly prevalent as an adjunct intervention in clinical settings. In our settings, **mindfulness is a natural human state of a judge/lawyer in which he/she uses discretion¹¹/creativity and attends to the present trial/legal issue.**

Mindfulness can be incorporated into other reforming modalities as part of an integrated approach to achieving justice/just legal services: legal practice development and transformation, law reform or judicial reform.

An effective legal and judicial reform strategy requires a comprehensive approach that includes: repeal (removal or reversal of a law), creation of new law, consolidation (combination of a number of laws into one), codification (collection and systematic arrangement, usually by subject, of the laws of a state or country), a program on judges training and education (including the mindfulness), improvements to appointment and promotion processes, better disciplining mechanisms, transparency in procedures and decision-making.¹²

An effective legal services development strategy at law firms requires a comprehensive approach that includes the inevitable digitisation and a program on lawyers training and education, including the mindfulness.

Unjust judicial discretion leads to injustice. Even judge's unjust thoughts can accumulate and/or spiral out of control, leading to injustice.

Here we base on **the mind–body problem**. We turn to the debate concerning the relationship between thought and mindfulness (consciousness) in the human mind, and the brain as part of the physical body. It is distinct from the question of how mind and body function chemically and physiologically, as that question presupposes an interactionist account of mind body relations. “The

⁷ <https://www.theconsciouslawyer.co.uk/mindful-lawyering/>

⁸ Kabat-Zinn, J. Wherever you go, there you are: Mindfulness meditation in everyday life. New York: Hyperion, 4 (1994)

⁹ Discretion is the selection of that which is just by the law.

Discretion is to discern through law what is just. Discretion in legal practice means the equitable decision of what is just and proper under the circumstances. It is the power of a judge, in certain matters, to decide in accordance with his own judgment of the equities for the cases, unhampered by inflexible rules of law. The latitude allowed to judges as to the action to be taken on certain facts.

¹⁰ https://mindfulness.au.dk/fileadmin/mindfulness.au.dk/Artikler/Santorelli_mbsr_standards_of_practice_2014.pdf

¹¹ *Discretio est discernere per legem quid sit justum.*

¹² <https://sdgaccountability.org/working-with-formal-processes/pursuing-law-reforms-strategic-litigation-and-legal-empowerment/#easy-footnote-bottom-1-611>

real distinction of mind and body based on their completely diverse natures is the root of the famous mind body problem: how can these two substances with completely different natures causally interact so as to give rise to a human being capable of having voluntary bodily motions and sensations?"¹³ This question arises when mind and body are considered as distinct, based on the premise that the mind and the body are fundamentally different in nature.

We advance to realize, however, that mindfulness (consciousness) can be of great benefit, as it can enable the judge/lawyer to become better able to separate himself from unjust/bad thoughts, emotions, and bodily sensations that may be present, often before they become too overwhelming, entering into judicial discretion/legal creativity.

Mindfulness-based interventions¹⁴ can be used to address a range of justice/good legal services concerns. Interventions have to train judges/lawyers how to put this practice into every trial/legal issue. Those judges/lawyers who are able to achieve this state of awareness may find it easier to then implement other reformal strategies. This article provides a basis for incorporating these interventions into achieving justice and judges/lawyers wellbeing.

Non judgmental way. A judge is a person. But a judge can't judge as an ordinary person. The mind of every person is a judging machine. Everything that we experience is filtered, categorized, and dealt with in some automatic way. Some things are judged as "good", so we grasp for more, and cling to what we have. Other things are judged as "bad", so we hide, resist, and run away from them. And everything else? That's judged as "neutral", so for the most part, we ignore it entirely. Judgment toward ourself, others, or events has impacted our life in ways that feel limiting, inauthentic, or harmful in some way. Setting down the judging mind is a refreshing weight off of judge's shoulders. A judge should let go of the automatic judgments that arise in his mind with every experience he/she has. He/she has to do justice, to use discretion as a judge, to apply and interpret legal norms as a judge, to judge as a judge¹⁵.

To be a judge/lawyer is a vocation of a special person. Here our starting point is that justice/good lawyering concerns the "democratic" foundations, stated by law, e.g judicial independence, the-rule-of-law state, access to fair justice.

In particular, we use insights from the scientific knowledge to examine how evolution of mind have informed and been informed by wider changes in science (labs) to achieve justice/good lawyering and well-being.

Max Planck says: "All matter originates and exists only by virtue of a force which brings the particle of an atom to vibration and holds this most minute solar system of the atom together. We must assume behind this force the existence of a conscious and intelligent mind. This mind is the matrix of all matter."¹⁶

Michio Kaku¹⁷ recently caused a small shock in the scientific community by claiming to have found evidence of the existence of an unknown and intelligent force that governs nature. "I came to the conclusion that we are in a world made up of rules created by an intelligence, not very different from a computer game, but of course, more complex," said the scientist.¹⁸

What we perceive with our five senses is not reality. Quantum physics has shown that space and time are illusions of perception. An experiment at the University of Manchester revealed that the

13 See: Skirry, Justin, Rene Descartes: The Mind-Body Distinction, Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy (2016).

14 In clinical settings the mindfulness-based interventions are generally aimed at relieving symptoms of stress, mental health concerns, and physical pain.

15 About the History, Meaning, and Use of the Words Justice and Judge (Jason Boatright) see in St. Mary's University School of Law: <https://commons.stmarytx.edu/thestmaryslawjournal/vol49/iss4/1/>

16 Planck Max, in Archimedes to Hawking: Laws of Science and the Great Minds Behind Them, Oxford University Press, 417 (19 March 2008)

17 Michio Kaku (January 24, 1947) is an American theoretical physicist, a professor of theoretical physics in the City College of New York and CUNY Graduate Center. He is famous for formulating the revolutionary string theory (model of fundamental physics which assumes that apparently specific material particles are actually "vibrational states"). He has written the New York Times best sellers Physics of the Impossible (2008), Physics of the Future (2011), and The Future of the Mind (2014).

18 <https://www.nbcnews.com/mach/science/michio-kaku-sees-amazing-things-our-future-except-those-scary-ncna851226>

shape of the interior of an atom is almost entirely empty space. The question then became how a judge/lawyer could possibly make justice/good lawyering sees him.

Our mindfulness (consciousness) does not exist in our brains or in our bodies, but this illusion of our individual bodies has manifested the idea that we all think independently from one another, that judges/lawyers all think independently from one another. With this understanding it seems possible to scientifically explain telepathy, clairvoyance, spiritual mediums related to the transfer of information between sources without physical means of communication phenomena.

When we understand that there is a common spiritual bond between all things in the universe and that we are all part of a divine intelligence, that judges are all part of the Universal Justice, this simple understanding will fill all the holes in modern justice included judicial discretion. A judge is just (fair) and his justice is immortal and timeless, once she/he identifies with the eternal reality the cosmic Justice, and consistent with the quantum vision, he will enter the new paradigms of quantum consciousness.¹⁹ A.Einstein confirmed: "A human being is a part of the whole called by us universe, a part limited in time and space. He experiences himself, his thoughts and feeling as something separated from the rest, a kind of optical delusion of his consciousness. This delusion is a kind of prison for us, restricting us to our personal desires and to affection for a few persons nearest to us. Our task must be to free ourselves from this prison by widening our circle of compassion to embrace all living creatures and the whole of nature in its beauty."²⁰

It's a mindfulness, spirit-matter's reality.

Pierre Teilhard de Chardin wrote on the reality of spirit-matter, inevitably translated into and confirmed by a structure of the spirit.²¹ It is worth quoting a passage from Chardin's *Evolution of Chastity*²²: it is in these invisible and, we might almost say, immaterial zones that we can look for true initiation into unity. The depths we attribute to matter are no more than the reflection of the peaks of spirit.²³ When our determination changes - Daisaku Ikeda²⁴ writes- everything will begin to move in the direction we want. The moment we decide to be victorious, every nerve and fiber in our being will immediately head towards our success. If, on the other hand, we think that *we will never make it* then in that instant, each of our cells will be emptied and will succumb. Neutrality and impartiality, justice, good lawyering, wellbeing, happiness, peace, conscience, everything are both the physical and spiritual aspects.

Professor Tiller²⁵'s research is summarized by himself with a thought of the Buddha: "All that we are is the result of what we have thought. The mind is everything. What we think we become".²⁶ Tiller conducted a rigorous experimental and theoretical study in field of psycho-energetic science,²⁷ developing ideas that go far beyond conventional scientific theories on the nature of human consciousness: he hypothesizes the existence of subtle energies that go beyond the four fundamental forces (the gravitational force, the electromagnetic force, the weak nuclear force and the strong

19 See: Valverde Raul, Quantum Consciousness & Spirit, *Journal of Consciousness Studies* 10(3):167-181 (April 2019).

20 <https://www.nytimes.com/1972/03/29/archives/the-einstein-papers-a-man-of-many-parts-the-einstein-papers-man-of.html>

21 Teilhard de Chardin Pierre, *Sketch of a Personalistic Universe* (1936). *Hymn of the Universe* (1961) is perhaps the work of Pierre Teilhard's that stands alone in that it contains almost no scientific treatises. It is mainly a poetic/spiritual testament to the world of spirit in matter. It envisions Christ as the heart of the universe, in the heart of matter.

22 See <https://teillard.com/tag/the-evolution-of-chastity/>

23 Teilhard de Chardin Pierre, *The Evolution of Chastity* (1934), as translated by René Hague in *Toward the Future* (1975)

24 Daisaku Ikeda (1928) is a Japanese philosopher, educator, Buddhist teacher and activist, third president of the national section of the Soka Gakkai in the period 1960 - 1979, is currently the president Ikeda, is defined as one of the most important Buddhist spiritual leaders of the second half of the 20th century and the 2000s, along with the Dalai Lama and Thích Nhất Hạnh.

25 William A. Tiller is emeritus professor of Science and Engineering of Materials, at Stanford University. Tiller spent 34 years in academia, after having been a consultative physicist at Westinghouse Research Laboratories for nine years, he has published over 250 scientific papers.

26 <https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/1296640-all-that-we-are-is-the-result-of-what-we>

27 Tiller William A, *Psychoenergetic Science* (2007)

nuclear force),²⁸ which work in concert with human consciousness. Tiller views humans as spiritual beings clothed in a bio-body, also endowed with enormous powers that they are not even aware of. Tiller believes that our consciousness is a by-product that is generated when the spirit enters dense matter. Tiller changed the way of thinking, from professor of materials science and engineering to professor of Human Transformation, who knows how to transform a problem into an opportunity. He's the Western Professor who, between a materialistic conception and the uniqueness of body and mind, chooses the uniqueness of body and mind, psychoenergetics, a matter that will probably become part of the physics of tomorrow. And to us, it's profound.

We advance a theory that as minimum, a judge has to have (legal) consciousness. The conventional existence of justice/judges wellbeing corresponds to the present ("living") level of a judge – to the level of his/her mindfulness (consciousness)/spirituality.

When we say about *the spirituality*, it is necessary to clarify what we mean. Spirituality is not a religion. There are some pretty clear ways in which religion and spirituality differ.²⁹ There are wider concerns about the idea of introducing practices, traditionally seen as having a strong religious association, into a secular setting. Norman Fisher³⁰ says: "These teachings are those of humanity, even though they may have originated 2,600 years ago. They can be taught in secular settings."³¹ Daniel J Siegel³² says: "Oftentimes, people hear the word 'mindfulness' and think 'religion', but the reality is that focusing our attention in this way is a biological process that promotes health – as a form of brain hygiene – not a religion. Various religions may encourage this health-promoting practice, but learning the skill of mindful awareness is simply a way of cultivating what we have defined as the integration of consciousness."

Spirituality depends on practice.³³

Spirituality develops when we dedicate our freedom to something greater and more important than ourselves, with that we identify ourselves.

In his Markings Dag Hammarskjöld wrote: "no life gave greater satisfaction than a life of selfless service to one's country and humanity. This service required the sacrifice of all private interests, but at the same time the courage to stand firm for one's convictions, accepting as troubles so happiness."³⁴

A judge develops spirituality when he dedicates his freedom to justice, with which he identifies himself. In order to achieve justice, a judge must go out of himself. The spiritual person is a mindful person. The spiritual (mindful) judge works on his own interiority, but uses the body, he is aware that as a body he depends on nature, as a judge he depends on the judiciary, law, the rule of law, he

28 <https://www.britannica.com/science/fundamental-interaction>

29 <https://au.reachout.com/articles/what-is-spirituality#:~:text=There%20are%20some%20pretty%20clear,sense%20of%20peace%20and%20purpose.>

30 Zoketsu Norman Fischer is an American poet, writer, and Soto Zen priest, teaching and practicing in the lineage of Shunryu Suzuki (Shunryu Suzuki, often called Suzuki Roshi. May, 1904 – 1971) was a Sōtō Zen monk and teacher who is renowned for founding the first Zen Buddhist monastery outside Asia (Tassajara Zen Mountain Center). Suzuki founded San Francisco Zen Center which, along with its affiliate temples, comprises one of the most influential Zen organizations in the United States. A book of his teachings, *Zen Mind, Beginner's Mind*, is one of the most popular books on Zen and Buddhism in the West). He is a Dharma heir of Sojun Mel Weitsman, from whom he received Dharma transmission in 1988. Fischer served as co-abbot of the San Francisco Zen Center from 1995–2000, after which he founded the Everyday Zen Foundation in 2000, a network of Buddhist practice group and related projects in Canada, the United States and Mexico (<http://everydayzen.org/about-everyday-zen/teachers/>). Fischer has published more than twenty-five books of poetry and non-fiction, as well as numerous poems, essays and articles in Buddhist magazines and poetry journals (<https://www.normanfischer.org/biography/>).

31 https://www.garrisoninstitute.org/images/Its_all_in_the_mind.pdf

32 Daniel J. Siegel (born July 17, 1957) is a clinical professor of psychiatry at the UCLA School of Medicine and executive director of the Mindful Awareness Research Centre.

33 See interview with Santikaro (Robert Larson), who had trained under the famous Thai Buddhist teacher, Buddhadasa Bhikkhu. According to him, in the west, there are three forms that mindfulness has been shaped into:

[https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?](https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xiLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACyXEo42DATwGm2DqjM0ujjORIHn5Qx-iTmzhDGIHx2JCCqKzs5gBcS0irWpIBxDnpzfrE167YQYyGHJOGg_PgaesyBq-XniWASmuLMb-S5YvN-CbdWKTvX9qjQPfs1ZZMU4D-NqM6vuoVM9IBLWTRfbOJFmXODfu2FJ-HbuZ4Ym)

https://www.huffpost.com/entry/is-there-anything-spiritu_b_8021384?guccounter=1&guce_referrer=aHR0cHM6Ly93d3cuZ29vZ2xiLmNvbS8&guce_referrer_sig=AQAAACyXEo42DATwGm2DqjM0ujjORIHn5Qx-iTmzhDGIHx2JCCqKzs5gBcS0irWpIBxDnpzfrE167YQYyGHJOGg_PgaesyBq-XniWASmuLMb-S5YvN-CbdWKTvX9qjQPfs1ZZMU4D-NqM6vuoVM9IBLWTRfbOJFmXODfu2FJ-HbuZ4Ym

34 <https://www.sgi-italia.org/pdf/Notizie/MaggioRadhakrishnanOsloSpeechFinalDraft.pdf>

knows that there is a human dimension of justice that cannot be reduced to the bios, nor to the judiciary, it is free, where the judge can act with discretion, he can create justice that was not there before, the judge knows that he can move away from a legal norm; he knows that freedom is precious and therefore must be cared for, supervised, disciplined, and that the justice happens if the judge relates to a larger dimension, to superior intelligence, to top values.

We hypothesize that justice/good lawyering in any settings depends significantly upon the synthesis of the “democratic” foundations, principles, established by law, and some top value that a judge/lawmaker/lawyer is devoted to serve. Among others, great Ivan Ilyin wrote about the idea of serving the highest value.³⁵ We have found the same idea in the thoughts of Pierre Teilhard de Chardin SJ³⁶, Teodosij Dobžanski³⁷, Anne Dambricourt-Malassé³⁸ and others.

We forward the idea that the Judicial Discretion/Legal Creativity ranks with the level of Mindfulness (*legal consciousness*). We contribute to debates whether the problems of Justice and Judges Wellbeing are resolved on the basis of the correspondence of Mindfulness (*legal consciousness*) to the basic legal principles of a state to counterbalance the liberal idea of universalism.³⁹

We advance the idea that conventional existence of Justice and Judges Wellbeing depends on the mindfulness (*legal consciousness*); the culture; political experience of a state in historical perspective; geographical location of a state; etc.

Law is a living organism.⁴⁰ It is based on a factual and social reality that is constantly changing.⁴¹ According to our conclusion the establishment of judicial discretion/legal creativity by the rule of law is not the judge\lawmaker`s whim but the result of development of state\community, law, mindfulness (spirituality). To what a judge\lawyer pays attention depends upon such development.⁴² In line with this interpretation, our analysis advises any specific system as for democratic states so for transition and developing economies and suggests that institutional development and academic research should aim at identifying the contextual circumstances which affect the costs and benefits of the different solutions.

We hypothesize that in Russia the democratic foundations, especially of justice, stated by law, but not followed from the historical, cultural, political development of Russia, result in the crisis of the legal consciousness of a judge\lawyer.⁴³

We advance the idea that the justice/wellbeing`s problems are the failure of judicial discretion/legal creativity and the result of the mindfulness (*legal consciousness*)`s deformation and blemish.

35 <https://www.tstu.ru/book/elib/pdf/st/2008/moskaleva.pdf>

36 Pierre Teilhard de Chardin SJ (1881 – 1955) was a French idealist philosopher and Jesuit Catholic priest who trained as a paleontologist and geologist and took part in the discovery of the Peking Man. He conceived the vitalist idea of the Omega Point (a maximum level of complexity and consciousness towards which he believed the universe was evolving), and he developed with Vladimir Vernadsky the concept of noosphere. Teilhard's ideas had a profound influence on the New Age movement. The idea of the Omega Point is developed in later writings, such as those of John David Garcia (1971), Paolo Soleri (1981), Frank Tipler (1994), and David Deutsch (1997).

37 Theodosius Grygorovych Dobzhansky (1900 – 1975) was a prominent Soviet-American geneticist and evolutionary biologist, and a central figure in the field of evolutionary biology for his work in shaping the modern synthesis.

38 Anne Dambricourt-Malassé (born in 1959), researcher in human palaeontology at the CNRS, Paris, France, secretary general of the Teilhard de Chardin Foundation, offers a bold thesis on the evolution of living things.

39 “By universalism, I mean the assumption that knowledge, justice and personal development are to be found in the universal rather than the particular; that the progression should be away from particular facts towards universal laws, away from particular judgements towards general principles, away from one's "parochial" origins towards a cosmopolitan sensibility or the universal fellowship of the human spirit. In each area, the universal is given priority.” See: Boyle James, *Universalism, Justice and Identity Politics: From Political Correctness to Constitutional Law* (2000), <https://law.duke.edu/boylesite/identity.htm>

40 Dickson Brian, *A Life in the Law: The Process of Judging*, 63 *Sask. L. Rev.* 373, 388 (2000), Cardozo Benjamin N., *The Paradoxes of Legal Science* 10–11 (Greenwood Press 1970) (1928).

41 Rehnquist William H, *The Changing Role of the Supreme Court*, 14 *Fla.St. U. L. Rev.*, 1.

42 Паркова О.А. *Judicial Discretion (Судейское усмотрение) (Usmotrenie Suda)*, Moscow, 64-199 (2005)

43 See about the issue: Silbey Susan S, *Studying legal consciousness: Building institutional theory from micro data*, *Droit et société* Volume 100, Issue 3, 733-788 (2018) https://www.cairn-int.info/article-E_DRS1_100_0733--studying-legal-consciousness-building.htm

In line with this point we hypothesize that *the Judicial Discretion/Legal Creativity is the art of law*.

We share the Charles Halpern⁴⁴ words, written in the context of the American legal system, applicable equally in a global context, because the difficulties and issues described by Halpern are faced by lawyers in jurisdictions across the world, including Italy and Russia: “Legal education and the legal profession, like society at large, are in a period of transition. Lawyers and law students today face unprecedented challenges, from upheaval in the legal market, to seismic shifts in health care, financial markets, the environment and other sectors. In order to thrive and effectively service their clients in this time of uncertainty, legal professionals need new skills, and I believe deeply that one of them is mindfulness, the ancient practice of moment-by-moment, non-judgmental awareness.”⁴⁵ Halpern and others like we advocating the potentially transformative effect of mindfulness in law are laying the foundation and paving the way for an urgently needed movement within the law that can, hopefully, only gain momentum. Such foundation and such way are applicable for every judge/lawmaker/lawyer, independently from the political settings, from a state. Charles Halpern says: “Lawyers survive in a sea of interconnected relationships. Emotional intelligence (EQ) is absolutely necessary. Mindfulness builds the muscle of EQ”.⁴⁶

Following Halpern’s idea, we are adamant that the present time is fertile ground for the practice of mindfulness and that it is teachable and learnable.

Little is done to educate and train lawyers – whose discretion/legal creativity tends to focus on the external, and to rely on ‘thinking’, ‘judging’ and ‘action’ – on the equal value and benefits of focusing on the internal, and relying on ‘not thinking’, ‘not judging’ and ‘not acting’.

This is exacerbated by the fact that *analytical personality types*⁴⁷, with a tendency to process information intellectually and look for guidance from external sources, are attracted to the field of law.

The *analytical personality type* is very deep and thoughtful. They’re serious and purposeful individuals. They set very high standards, so they have very high standards of performance personally and professionally. Analyticals are orderly and organized. They also tend to have that really dry but witty sense of humor. Analytical strengths are that they are perfectionists. They want things done right and they want them done right the first time. They’re neat and tidy individuals. Analyticals are economical, and they are self-disciplined. Analytical weaknesses are that they can be moody, critical, and negative. Analyticals can be indecisive and they over-analyze everything. Their perfectionism can also manifest as a weakness at times, as they can be guilty of making their pursuit of perfection stall completion.

We consider that the sincerity is the basis of mindfulness in law, following the "Sincerity is the foundation of spiritual life," of Albert Schweitzer.⁴⁸ Sincerity is the basis of the Mediterranean Lifestyle.

The analysis we carried, although still incomplete, suggests not only that the concepts of justice/good lawyering and judges/lawyers wellbeing needs a better definition, but that its main dimensions, including the phenomenon of judicial discretion/legal creativity with the special

44 Charles Halpern is a lawyer, activist, author, educator, and meditation practitioner. He also served as the founding dean of CUNY School of Law, and as a faculty member of various prominent law schools across the country. Halpern is considered a pioneer in public interest law, responsible for various entrepreneurial and educational initiatives that contributed to legal, academic, social justice, and contemplative communities. He is founder of the Initiative for Mindfulness in Law (an innovative programme exploring the benefits of mindfulness to legal education and law practice at Berkeley University, California) and one of the key thought-leaders for the mindfulness and law movement in the US, Halpern’s book, *Making Waves and Riding the Currents: Activism and the Practice of Wisdom*, tells the story of how he brought public interest activism, mindfulness, and meditation into law schools and courthouses across the United States. https://greatergood.berkeley.edu/profile/charles_halpern

45 <https://www.theconsciouslawyer.co.uk/mindful-lawyering/>

46 <https://www.theconsciouslawyer.co.uk/mindful-lawyering/>

47 See: <https://crestcom.com/blog/2015/11/24/4-personality-types-that-all-leaders-should-learn-to-recognize/#:~:text=1.-,Analytical.Analyticals%20are%20orderly%20and%20organized.>

48 Ludwig Philipp Albert Schweitzer OM (1875 – 1965) was an Alsatian polymath. He received the 1952 Nobel Peace Prize for his philosophy of "Reverence for Life".

attitude to mindfulness (legal) consciousness)), to the Mediterranean Style of Life should be taken into account for their different impact. Just imagine — understanding how Mediterranean Style of Life alone can produce mental clarity, good health, longevity of lawyers/judges/professionals/clients/everybody and Justice/Good Lawyering!